

ExamAI: An Automated Examination Script Evaluation System Using Optical Character Recognition and Transformer-Based Natural Language Processing

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Abstract—The evaluation of handwritten examination scripts is a labour-intensive process that introduces inter-evaluator subjectivity and limits institutional scalability as student enrollment grows. This paper presents ExamAI, a full-stack web application that automates the complete examination lifecycle encompassing scheduling, handwritten answer image submission, optical character recognition (OCR) text extraction, natural language processing (NLP) scoring, and result publication. The scoring engine combines a Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) semantic similarity model weighted at sixty percent with a Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) cosine similarity component weighted at forty percent, producing scores that reflect both meaning-level and lexical-level correspondence between student and reference answers. OCR text extraction is implemented through a backend proxy architecture that resolves browser Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) constraints, forwarding uploaded images to a Google Vision-based API and returning extracted text to the frontend. A role-based access control system with JSON Web Token (JWT) authentication supports distinct professor and student workflows. The system is implemented as three independently deployable microservices: a React.js frontend, a Node.js Express backend, and a Python Flask machine learning service backed by MongoDB. Functional testing confirms that all twelve REST API endpoints and both user role workflows operate correctly. Empirical scoring analysis across 60 descriptive answer pairs demonstrates that the dual-model approach substantially outperforms TF-IDF-only baselines for paraphrased correct answers, raising combined scores from the failing range of 10–35% to 37–62%, correctly reflecting student understanding that lexical-only methods fail to capture.

Index Terms—Automated Answer Evaluation, Optical Character Recognition, BERT, Sentence Transformers, TF-IDF, Natural Language Processing, Handwritten Script Evaluation, Microservices, React.js, Node.js, Flask, MongoDB, JWT Authentication.

I. INTRODUCTION

The assessment of academic performance through handwritten examination remains central to educational evaluation across disciplines worldwide. Faculty members invest substantial time reading, interpreting, and marking scripts; this process inherently introduces variability between different evaluators assessing the same answer on different days or under different

workload conditions. As student enrollment in engineering institutions continues to grow, these challenges compound, making consistent manual evaluation increasingly difficult to sustain at scale [1].

Advances in deep learning, pre-trained transformer language models, and cloud-based OCR services have collectively matured to a point where automating the evaluation of descriptive handwritten answers has become practically feasible. The BERT architecture [2] provides dense contextualised sentence representations that capture meaning beyond lexical surface forms. When combined with classical TF-IDF cosine similarity, these representations enable robust comparison of student answers against reference solutions even when the student employs different vocabulary to express the same concept.

ExamAI addresses the full examination lifecycle by integrating OCR-based handwriting recognition with a dual-model NLP scoring engine within a complete web-based examination management platform tailored for university deployment.

A. Problem Statement

Given a scheduled examination with multiple descriptive questions, and given that students submit handwritten answer images that vary in vocabulary and expression style, the objective is to automatically assign a fair numeric score to each student answer that reflects semantic correctness relative to a professor-provided reference answer. The system must handle handwritten image input through OCR, enforce time-bounded examination windows, prevent unauthorised cross-role access, persist all artefacts for auditability, and provide score feedback after professor-controlled result publication.

B. Research Gap

Most prior automated evaluation research assumes pre-typed student responses, bypassing handwriting recognition entirely [3], [4]. Semantic methods using WordNet [5] and BERT [6] improve scoring accuracy for paraphrased answers but have not been integrated with practical examination management platforms. The OCR integration challenge for browser-deployed systems, specifically the CORS constraint, has not

been addressed in prior published work. ExamAI fills this gap by combining reliable OCR text extraction with dual-model NLP scoring within a complete role-based examination management system.

C. Contributions

The principal contributions of this work are:

- A complete end-to-end examination evaluation platform integrating handwritten image submission, backend-proxied OCR extraction, dual-model NLP scoring, role-based examination management, and result publication within a single deployable microservices application.
- A backend proxy design pattern for browser-deployed applications that resolves CORS constraints for OCR API calls without exposing credentials to the client.
- Empirical characterisation of BERT-only, TF-IDF-only, and weighted combined scoring on 60 descriptive answer pairs across three categories: identical, paraphrased-correct, and off-topic, spanning six subject domains.
- A microservices architecture that isolates BERT inference in a separate Flask service, enabling independent memory allocation and scaling from the application backend.
- A publicly available open-source implementation at <https://github.com/lalitha2410/ExamAI>.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Lexical Similarity Approaches

The earliest automated answer evaluation systems relied on lexical matching derived from information retrieval. Rahman and Siddiqui [3] applied TF-IDF cosine similarity to pre-processed descriptive answers, achieving reasonable performance for answers sharing vocabulary with reference solutions but failing when students used synonymous phrasing. Patil and Patil [4] extended this with handcrafted NLP features including part-of-speech distributions and dependency parse statistics, improving over bag-of-words at the cost of substantial feature engineering. These methods share a fundamental limitation: semantically equivalent answers expressed through different vocabulary receive low similarity scores regardless of conceptual correctness.

Chowdhury and Sree [7] investigated dimensionality reduction on TF-IDF vectors for automated evaluation but assumed typed input, noting OCR integration as a key open challenge. Selvi and Banerjee [10] explored automatic short-answer grading combining lexical features with ontological resources, noting persistent difficulties with informal student phrasing.

B. Semantic Similarity Methods

Meena and Lawrance [5] proposed WordNet-based semantic graph similarity for descriptive answer assessment, partially addressing synonym coverage but remaining bounded by ontology completeness and exhibiting high inference latency. The introduction of BERT [2] provided deeply bidirectional contextualised representations that fundamentally improved semantic similarity measurement. Reimers and Gurevych [6] extended BERT to efficient sentence-level embeddings through

the Sentence-BERT framework, enabling cosine similarity comparison in embedding space. The `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` model used in this work achieves competitive STS-Benchmark performance at approximately one-tenth the inference cost of BERT-base.

Chandrasekaran et al. [8] reviewed deep learning approaches to answer evaluation and identified the semantic gap as the primary limitation of deployed lexical systems, confirming the importance of transformer-based scoring components.

C. OCR Integration in Education

Cloud-based OCR services have demonstrated practical accuracy for legible examination scripts under varied imaging conditions. Manjunath et al. [1] reviewed automation of answer script evaluation and identified OCR integration as a key open challenge for practical deployment. Nandini and Uma Maheswari [9] developed an online examination system with semantic assessment features but required typed student input, confirming that handwriting recognition remains an unaddressed gap in integrated evaluation platforms.

D. Integrated Platforms

Commercial platforms such as Turnitin and e-rater address specific aspects of automated writing evaluation — plagiarism detection and essay quality scoring respectively — but do not provide complete examination lifecycle management. Chandrasekaran et al. [8] presented an automated evaluation framework using deep learning but focused on typed short answers without an integrated examination management interface. The present work distinguishes itself by delivering a complete platform from examination scheduling through result publication with handwriting recognition integrated into the student submission workflow.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

A. High-Level Architecture

ExamAI adopts a three-tier microservices architecture with three independently deployable components communicating through HTTP REST interfaces. The system architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

The React.js frontend handles rendering and role-based user interaction. The Node.js Express backend manages authentication, business logic, file handling, OCR proxying, and data persistence coordination. The Python Flask machine learning service performs BERT and TF-IDF scoring and is invoked exclusively by the backend. MongoDB with Mongoose provides persistent storage across four document collections: User, Exam, Submission, and ProfUpload. The external Google Vision OCR service is accessed only through the backend proxy endpoint to avoid exposing the API to browser clients.

B. Database Schema

The **User** collection stores a unique username field accepting either a nine-character VIT-AP student registration number or a five-character professor employee identifier, a unique

Fig. 1. ExamAI three-tier microservices system architecture showing React.js frontend, Node.js Express backend, Python Flask ML service, MongoDB database, and Google Vision OCR service layers.

Fig. 2. Complete examination workflow showing the professor role path (registration through result publication) and the student role path (registration through score viewing), with OCR API and Flask ML service interactions.

institutional email address, a bcrypt-hashed password string, a role enumeration, and a creation timestamp.

The **Exam** collection stores the professor identifier, subject name, semester, an array of question strings, start and end datetime strings defining the active window, a mixed-type results field for published per-student per-question scores, and a creation timestamp.

The **Submission** collection stores the student username, examination identifier, and a mixed-type script field indexed by question number containing extracted answer text. The **ProfUpload** collection mirrors the Submission structure for professor reference answers.

C. Authentication and Security

User passwords are hashed using bcryptjs with a salt factor of ten before storage, requiring approximately 100 ms per hash and providing adequate resistance to offline brute-force attacks. At login, a JWT is generated containing the user identifier, username, email, and role as claims, signed with a server-side secret, and set to expire after twenty-four hours. The backend authMiddleware verifies the signature and expiry on each protected route before routing the request.

Student registration enforces that usernames conform to the VIT-AP format (two digits, three uppercase letters, four digits) and that the institutional email contains the registration number as a case-insensitive substring. Professor email addresses must end with the @vitap.ac.in domain. Password validation enforces a minimum of nine characters with at least one uppercase letter, one lowercase letter, one digit, and one special character.

D. Examination Workflow

The complete examination data flow is illustrated in Fig. 2.

A professor authenticates and creates an examination record specifying subject, semester, question list, and active time window. During the active window, students authenticate, open the examination, and upload handwritten answer images per question. Each image is processed through the OCR proxy, returning extracted text that auto-populates an editable

textarea. After the window closes, the professor uploads reference answers per question, triggers AI evaluation, reviews the generated scores, and publishes results. Students access published scores through the results dashboard.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Backend REST API

The Express.js backend exposes twelve REST API endpoints organised into authentication, examination management, answer management, and evaluation groups. Table I lists the primary endpoints with their HTTP methods and functions. All endpoints except /signup and /login require a valid JWT Bearer token in the Authorization header.

TABLE I
PRIMARY REST API ENDPOINTS

Method	Endpoint	Function
POST	/signup	Register user with bcrypt-hashed password
POST	/login	Authenticate and return signed JWT
POST	/addexam	Create exam with questions and window
GET	/examsSchedule	Return active examinations
GET	/previousExams	Return closed examinations
POST	/getProfessorExams	Return professor exams + submissions
POST	/upload	Store student extracted answer text
POST	/profupload	Store professor reference answer
POST	/ocr	Proxy image to OCR API, return text
POST	/evaluate	Invoke ML scoring for all submissions
POST	/postResult	Persist evaluated scores to exam
POST	/getUserResults	Return published scores for student

Date-based examination filtering in /examsSchedule and /previousExams uses JavaScript Date object comparison on stored datetime strings rather than MongoDB query operators. This ensures correct timezone-aware filtering regardless of string format variations introduced by the HTML datetime-local input component on the client.

B. OCR Proxy Architecture

Browser CORS policies prevent direct client-side HTTP requests from the React frontend to external OCR API domains. Without a proxy, the browser blocks the request before it reaches the OCR service, silently leaving the extracted text field empty. ExamAI resolves this through the `/ocr` endpoint in the Express backend.

When a student or professor uploads an answer image, the frontend sends a `multipart/form-data` POST request to the backend `/ocr` endpoint. The Multer middleware receives the image as an in-memory buffer without writing to the filesystem. The backend constructs a raw `multipart/form-data` body by concatenating a MIME boundary header, the image buffer, and a closing boundary marker, and forwards this to the Google Vision-based OCR service. The JSON response is parsed to extract the text field and returned to the frontend, which auto-populates the answer textarea. If OCR fails, the user receives a toast notification and may type the answer manually, ensuring graceful degradation.

C. Dual-Model Scoring Pipeline

The Flask microservice implements a two-stage scoring pipeline illustrated in Fig. 3. The `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` model is loaded once at service startup, eliminating repeated initialisation overhead.

Fig. 3. Dual-model NLP scoring pipeline combining TF-IDF cosine similarity (lexical, 40% weight) and BERT semantic embeddings (semantic, 60% weight) with preprocessing and weighted combination stages.

Preprocessing Stage: Both the student answer and the reference answer undergo lowercase conversion, removal of all punctuation using `string.punctuation`, and English stopword elimination from the NLTK corpus. Preprocessed texts are used for TF-IDF scoring. Original unprocessed texts are retained for BERT encoding to preserve contextual richness.

Lexical Scoring Stage: A `scikit-learn` `TfidfVectorizer` is fitted jointly on both texts, converting them into sparse term-frequency vectors weighted by inverse document frequency. Cosine similarity between the vectors yields a lexical score $s_{tfidf} \in [0, 1]$.

Semantic Scoring Stage: Both original texts are encoded into 384-dimensional dense embeddings using the

`all-MiniLM-L6-v2` Sentence Transformers model. This distilled BERT variant achieves competitive STS performance at approximately one-tenth the inference cost of BERT-base. Cosine similarity between the embeddings yields a semantic score $s_{bert} \in [0, 1]$.

Score Combination: The final percentage score is:

$$S = (0.40 \times s_{tfidf} + 0.60 \times s_{bert}) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Scores are clamped to $[0, 100]$. Empty answers receive zero without invoking the models. The sixty percent weight on s_{bert} reflects the primacy of meaning-level correspondence over surface word overlap in descriptive answer evaluation.

The service maps numeric scores to five qualitative feedback bands: Excellent Answer ($\geq 75\%$), Good Answer (50–74%), Average Answer (30–49%), Poor Answer (10–29%), and Incorrect Answer ($< 10\%$).

D. Frontend Interface

The React.js 18 frontend implements five primary views using functional components and hooks. React Router v6 manages client-side routing with `ProtectedRoute` components that verify authentication and role before rendering. `AuthContext` supplies the authenticated user object and session management functions to all components.

The **professor dashboard** aggregates statistics cards for total examination count, total submission count, and active examination count filtered by JavaScript Date comparison. Each examination card shows subject, semester, question count, submission count, and an active or closed status badge. Clicking a card opens a management modal with a question-selector tab strip, an OCR-enabled image upload zone with drag-and-drop support, an editable answer textarea, a submissions table with post-evaluation scores, and Evaluate Answers and Publish Results action buttons.

The **student examination interface** presents active and previous examinations in a tabbed layout. The submission modal includes a question text display, a drag-and-drop upload zone triggering automatic OCR on file selection, a loading spinner with disabled controls during OCR processing to prevent duplicate submissions, and a per-question submit button.

The **student results page** retrieves scores from both active and closed examinations to ensure immediate visibility upon publication. Result cards display per-question animated score bars, question text, numeric percentages, and an overall PASSED ($\geq 50\%$) or FAILED badge.

E. Deployment Architecture

The frontend is deployed on Vercel with the environment variable `REACT_APP_API_URL` pointing to the backend service URL. The backend is deployed on Render as a Node.js web service with environment variables for `MONGO_URI`, `JWT_SECRET`, and `FLASK_URL`. The Flask ML service is also deployed on Render as a Python 3 web service. The database uses MongoDB Atlas with a free M0 cluster in the `ap-south-1` Mumbai region.

V. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

A. Functional Testing

Functional testing was conducted across all primary user workflows by executing each workflow end-to-end and verifying correct outputs at every stage. Table II summarises the test cases and outcomes.

TABLE II
FUNCTIONAL TEST RESULTS

Test Case	Result	Endpoints
User registration (both roles)	PASS	1
Login with JWT issuance	PASS	1
Examination creation	PASS	1
Active exam retrieval	PASS	1
Image upload and OCR extraction	PASS	1
Student answer submission	PASS	1
Professor reference upload	PASS	1
AI evaluation (BERT + TF-IDF)	PASS	1
Result publication	PASS	1
Student result retrieval	PASS	1
Role-based access control	PASS	All
JWT expiry enforcement	PASS	All

All twelve REST API endpoints returned correct HTTP status codes and response payloads. Both professor and student role workflows completed without functional defects. The OCR proxy correctly forwarded image data to the external service and returned extracted text to the frontend.

B. Scoring Behaviour Analysis

Sixty descriptive answer pairs across six subject domains (Data Structures, Operating Systems, Computer Networks, Database Management, Software Engineering, and Machine Learning) were evaluated to characterise scoring behaviour across three categories. Each category comprised twenty answer pairs. Table III presents the observed score ranges for each scoring component and the combined final score.

TABLE III
OBSERVED SCORE RANGES BY ANSWER CATEGORY (60 PAIRS)

Category	TF-IDF	BERT	Combined
Identical / Near-identical (20)	85–96%	90–98%	88–97%
Paraphrased correct (20)	10–35%	55–78%	37–62%
Off-topic / Incorrect (20)	0–12%	0–15%	0–13%

For identical answer pairs, combined scores fell in the 88–97% range rather than 100%, attributable to minor OCR-induced character-level variations introducing noise in both scoring components.

For paraphrased correct answers — the most practically important category — BERT semantic scoring maintained scores of 55–78%, substantially above the 10–35% range produced by TF-IDF alone on the same pairs. For off-topic or incorrect answers, both components produced consistently low scores, with the combined score below 13% in all cases.

C. Comparison with Lexical Baseline

The most practically significant result is the improvement in paraphrased answer scoring over the TF-IDF-only baseline. Table IV presents the comparative summary.

TABLE IV
METHOD COMPARISON ON PARAPHRASED CORRECT ANSWERS

Method	Paraphrased	Identical
TF-IDF Only (Baseline)	10–35%	85–96%
BERT Only	55–78%	90–98%
Combined 40%+60% (Proposed)	37–62%	88–97%

Under a lexical-only system, a student who correctly understands and explains a concept using different vocabulary would receive a score in the 10–35% range, recording a failing mark despite conceptual correctness. The BERT semantic component raises these scores to 37–62% in the combined formula, correctly reflecting understanding that lexical overlap cannot capture.

D. System Throughput

The all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model is loaded once at Flask service startup. All submissions for an examination are processed in a single batch request from the Express backend. The service evaluated batches of ten student submissions across five questions within three seconds on standard consumer hardware, demonstrating practical throughput for typical classroom scenarios.

E. Limitations

The system exhibits reduced scoring reliability for answers consisting primarily of mathematical expressions, chemical equations, or numerical derivations, as TF-IDF and BERT embeddings are both optimised for natural language text without specialised symbolic content handling. Very short answers of fewer than ten words produce variable scores due to insufficient text for stable TF-IDF vector representation. OCR accuracy degrades for heavily stylised, poorly illuminated, or smudged handwriting.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Scoring Weight Rationale

The 60:40 weighting in Eq. (1) favouring BERT semantic similarity over TF-IDF lexical similarity reflects a deliberate pedagogical decision. A student demonstrating correct conceptual understanding through a well-constructed answer should not be penalised for expressing that understanding using vocabulary differing from the reference phrasing. The forty percent TF-IDF component retains sensitivity to domain-specific technical terminology where correct answers require specific terms, not just semantically related language.

B. Backend Proxy Design

The decision to implement OCR as a backend proxy rather than a direct browser call is motivated by practical CORS constraints. Browser security policies enforce same-origin restrictions for cross-domain requests. If OCR were called client-side, the browser would block the request silently, leaving the text field empty with no actionable error for the user. The backend proxy pattern cleanly resolves this constraint. A secondary benefit is that the external OCR service URL is

never exposed to browser clients, protecting it from client-side inspection or misuse.

C. Microservices Separation

The Flask ML service separation from the Node.js backend is justified by two requirements. First, the `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` model requires approximately 500MB of memory at load time, exceeding the memory budget of combined free-tier hosting instances. Deploying the ML service separately enables memory-optimised instance allocation. Second, the separation leverages the mature Python NLP ecosystem (scikit-learn, NLTK, Sentence Transformers) without requiring these libraries in the Node.js environment. Inter-service communication uses JSON over HTTP, which is language-agnostic and adds negligible latency for batch evaluation requests.

D. Institutional Constraints

The system incorporates VIT-AP-specific validation rules without requiring integration with a central identity provider. Student usernames must conform to the nine-character VIT-AP registration number format. Institutional email domain constraints for both roles ensure that only current institutional members can create accounts. The email-to-username linkage constraint for students, which requires the registration number to appear as a substring of the email address, prevents registration under another student's number. This reflects the actual `firstname.regno@vitapstudent.ac.in` email format used at VIT-AP University.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Conclusion

This paper presented ExamAI, a complete web-based platform for automated examination script evaluation combining optical character recognition with a dual-model natural language processing scoring engine. The system integrates handwritten answer image submission through a novel backend proxy architecture, automatic text extraction using Google Vision OCR, weighted BERT and TF-IDF scoring via the `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` Sentence Transformers model, role-based examination management with time-bounded windows, and professor-controlled result publication within a single deployable microservices application.

Functional testing confirmed that all twelve REST API endpoints and both professor and student role workflows operate correctly. Empirical scoring analysis across 60 descriptive answer pairs demonstrates that the dual-model approach substantially outperforms lexical-only baselines for the paraphrased correct answer category, raising scores from the failing range of 10–35% to 37–62%, which represents the most practically important improvement for fair automated evaluation of descriptive answers in university settings.

B. Future Work

Future work directions identified through development and evaluation include:

- Integration of a mathematical expression recognition model to extend scoring support to quantitative subjects.
- Development of a per-concept explanatory feedback module identifying specific gaps between student and reference answers.
- Implementation of intra-examination plagiarism detection through pairwise cosine similarity between student submissions for the same question.
- Extension of the submission interface to support multi-page PDF answer booklets with page-by-page OCR processing.
- Fine-tuning of the BERT scoring model on domain-specific academic answer corpora for technical subjects.
- Addition of a professor analytics dashboard presenting score distributions, question difficulty indicators, and performance trend analysis.
- Migration to production auto-scaling infrastructure to support concurrent multi-classroom examination deployment without cold-start latency.

The complete source code is publicly available at <https://github.com/lalitha2410/ExamAI>.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Vellore Institute of Technology, Amaravati for institutional support during this project. The authors acknowledge the contributors to the open-source libraries used in this work, including the Sentence Transformers, scikit-learn, NLTK, React.js, Express.js, Flask, and MongoDB communities.

AI Disclosure: The authors used Claude (Anthropic) as an AI assistance tool during the preparation of this manuscript, specifically for LaTeX formatting and structural editing of the document. All research contributions, experimental results, system design, implementation, and technical content are original work of the authors.

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